

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SHADE SELECTION BY POST-GRADUATE STUDENTS UNDER DIFFERENT LIGHTING CONDITIONS

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Abstract: Achieving successful esthetic dentistry that satisfies patients and positively influences their personality is not possible without proper shade selection—whether for direct or indirect dental restorations. Choosing the correct shade is one of the most crucial and fascinating steps in recreating the natural appearance of teeth. The purpose of this study is to provide information on the knowledge and practice of shade matching along with comparison of shade selection under natural light and clinical light for restorations and prosthesis.

Keywords: Clinical light, Natural light, Shade matching, Shade selection, Vita 3D Master,

I. INTRODUCTION:

Over the past decades, aesthetics has assumed a new prominence in modern dentistry, appearing to portray an individual's personality.^[1] Hence establishing a natural dental appearance now constitutes a vital task in the specialties of prosthodontics and conservative dentistry. Generally, shade is a combination of three factors: hue, value and chroma. Hue is what distinguishes one colour from another; value indicates the lightness of a colour ranging from pure black to pure white while chroma is the degree of colour saturation that describes the strength, intensity or vividness.^[2] Shade matching performance of dentists and transmitting it to the laboratory is an essential factor in natural tooth color reproduction. The visual method of shade determination is commonly used in the clinics and training institutions. It is a quick and cost-effective method. When using the visual method, the tooth and the shade guide should be viewed simultaneously under the same lighting conditions. However, most of the clinicians perform the process of color matching in the clinic under the clinical light condition or in natural daylight.^[3]

This study therefore aims to provide information on the knowledge and practice of shade matching along with comparison of shade selection under natural light and clinical light for restorations and prosthesis.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Eleven postgraduate students, 5 from department of Prosthodontics and 6 from department of Endodontics were participated in the study. All students performed Ishahar's tests to determine color deficiency. In order to eliminate possible bias caused due to color vision defect, participants involved with color vision deficiency were excluded from study.

Questionnaire:

10 questions regarding shade selection and Vita 3D Master shade guide were prepared. Prior shade matching, each participant was provided with a link to google form in order to fill the questionnaire. After submitting the questionnaire, participants were given 5 concealed shades to match under natural light and clinical light.

Shade guide preparation:

Vita Toothguide 3D master shade guide (Vita Zahnfabrik, Bad Sackingen, Germany) was used in the study. From first shade guide 5 shades were randomly selected from each row. The identification codes were concealed and 1-5 numbers were allocated for each shade. Each student was given 10 minutes to decrease error possibility. Each student matched the shade under two lights, 1. Natural light 2. Clinical light.

The clinical lighting condition was a compound of natural light and fluorescent light as well as incandescent. Shade matching under natural light was conducted between the hours of 9 am to 3 pm. Having completed the matching of selected items (shade tabs with the identification code concealed) to a vita shade guide, the chosen shade tabs were recorded and the correct matches were counted.

The statistical analysis was done using Mann-Whitney U Test and Chi square Test.

Fig. 1 Concealed shades and Full Vita 3D Master shade guide

III. RESULT

A total of 11 PG students, 5 from Department of Prosthodontics and 6 from Department of Endodontics were participated in this study with mean age of 27.18 ± 1.25 . The age of participants from endodontics was 27.83 ± 1.33 and from prosthodontics was 26.4 ± 0.55 which was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). (**Table 2**) None of the PG students withdraw from the study after participation. Prior shade selection, participants were provided with the questionnaire regarding shade matching and Vita 3D Master shade guide via Google form. Participants were needed to fill the questionnaire first based on their knowledge. The recorded responses were then collected in a tabulated format. Wrong responses were designated as 0 while right responses were designated as 1. (**Table 1**) After questionnaire filling each participant were provided with the concealed shades and a full Vita 3D Master shade guide for shade matching in natural and clinical light. (**Figure 1**) Recorded responses were collected in tabulated format and designated as 0 for wrong response and 1 for right response.

Comparison of knowledge regarding shade matching and Vita 3D Master shade guide was done. The mean response of participants for various questions regarding shade selection was observed. (**Table 3 and Figure 3**) It was noted that when enquired “In which cases shade selection should be done?” all participants from both departments gave correct response. Similarly, for “Preferred time for shade selection” 6 participants from endodontics and 3 from prosthodontics gave correct response and the difference between them was non-significant ($p > 0.05$). For questions related to Vita 3D master shade guide such as “On what dimension Vita 3D Master shade guide is based for?” and “What does L, M, R present on the shade guide stands for?”, none of the participants from both the departments gave correct answer. The mean knowledge regarding shade selection in Endodontics group was 5 ± 0.89 which was slightly higher than prosthodontics group (4.6 ± 1.52) but this difference was insignificant ($p > 0.05$) (**Table 4 and Figure 4**)

Comparison of shade selection done by students from department of Prosthodontics and Endodontics under natural and clinical light was done. In natural light natural light 3 participants from Prosthodontic department and 6 from Endodontics department gave correct response for A and this difference was statistically not significant ($p > 0.05$). For D and E shade tab, none

of the participants from department of Endodontics did the correct shade matching. The differences for shade selections for shade tab **E** was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) (**Table 5 and Figure 5**).

In clinical light, none of the participants from department of Endodontics did the correct shade matching for shade tab **E**. For shade tab **C**, four participants from department of Prosthodontics did the correct shade matching while from department of Endodontics only one participant did the correct shade matching. This difference was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) (**Table 6 and Figure 6**).

In natural light, “**3M2**” shade tab showed the maximum variation in matching. For shade “**4M1**” 81.8% participants selected the correct shade tab. While for shade tab “**4R1.5**” only 18.2% participants selected the correct shade tab (**Table 7**).

In clinical light, shade tabs “**4M1**” and “**4I2.5**” showed the maximum variations. For the shade tabs “**4M1**”, “**3M2**”, “**4R2.5**” 45.5% participants selected the correct shade tab. While for shade tab “**3L2.5**” only 18.2% participants selected the correct shade tab (**Table 8**).

TABLE I: DATA COLLECTED DURING the STUDY

Participants	Age	Department	Sex	Natural light					Clinical light					Do you do shade selection?	In which cases shade selection should be done?	Preferred time for shade selection	Which shade guide do you use more often for shade selection?	What lighting condition do you prefer for shade selection?	On what dimension Vita 3D Master shade guide is based for?	Select the sequence of shade selection using Vita 3D master shade guide	How will you select the lightness of the tooth?	What does L, M, R present on the shade guide stands for?	Correct order of Shade communication with other dental professional or prescription for laboratory professional
				A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E										
I	27	Prosthodontics	Female	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
II	27	Prosthodontics	Female	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0
III	26	Prosthodontics	Male	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
IV	26	Prosthodontics	Female	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
V	26	Prosthodontics	Female	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
VI	29	Endodontics	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
VII	26	Endodontics	Female	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
VIII	29	Endodontics	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
IX	27	Endodontics	Female	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
X	27	Endodontics	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
XI	29	Endodontics	Female	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1

1- Correct response, 0- Wrong response

TABLE II: COMPARISON of MEAN AGE of STUDY PARTICIPANTS from BOTH DEPARTMENTS by MANN-WHITNEY U TEST

	N	Mean	SD	p-value
Endodontics	6	27.83	1.33	0.003
Prosthodontics	5	26.4	0.55	
Total	11	27.18	1.25	

Fig. 2 Comparison of mean age of study participants from both departments

TABLE III: COMPARISON of KNOWLEDGE REGARDING SHADE SELECTION in BOTH DEPARTMENTS by CHI-SQUARE TEST

Items	Department	Response		p-value
		Wrong	Correct	
In which cases shade selection should be done?	Prosthodontics	0	5	NA
	Endodontics	0	6	
Preferred time for shade selection	Prosthodontics	2	3	0.087
	Endodontics	0	6	
Which shade guide do you use more often for shade selection?	Prosthodontics	0	5	NA
	Endodontics	0	6	
What lighting condition do you prefer for shade selection?	Prosthodontics	4	1	0.887
	Endodontics	5	1	
On what dimension Vita 3D Master shade guide is based for?	Prosthodontics	5	0	NA
	Endodontics	6	0	
Select the sequence of shade selection using Vita 3D master shade guide	Prosthodontics	4	1	0.887
	Endodontics	5	1	
How will you select the lightness of the tooth?	Prosthodontics	3	2	0.74
	Endodontics	3	3	
What does L, M, R present on the shade guide stands for?	Prosthodontics	5	0	NA
	Endodontics	6	0	
Correct order of Shade communication with other dental professional or prescription for laboratory professional	Prosthodontics	4	1	0.887
	Endodontics	5	1	

Fig. 3 Comparison of knowledge (correct response) regarding shade selection in both departments

TABLE IV: COMPARISON of MEAN KNOWLEDGE REGARDING SHADE SELECTION in BOTH DEPARTMENTS by MANN-WHITNEY U TEST

Department	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
Endodontics	5	0.89	0.078
Prosthodontics	4.6	1.52	

Fig. 4 Comparison of mean knowledge regarding shade selection in both departments

TABLE V: COMPARISON of SHADE SELECTION in NATURAL LIGHT by PARTICIPANTS from BOTH DEPARTMENTS by CHI-SQUARE TEST

Department	A		B		C		D		E	
	Wrong	Correct	Wrong	Correct	Wrong	Correct	Wrong	Correct	Wrong	Correct
Prosthodontics	1	3	2	2	3	4	3	2	2	3
Endodontics	1	6	0	5	1	5	6	0	6	0
Total	2	9	2	7	4	9	9	2	8	3
p-value	0.887		0.087		0.137		0.887		0.026*	

*0<0.05; significant

Fig.5 Comparison of shade selection in natural light by participants from both departments

TABLE VI: COMPARISON of SHADE SELECTION in CLINICAL LIGHT by PARTICIPANTS from BOTH DEPARTMENTS by CHI-SQUARE TEST

Department	A		B		C		D		E	
	Wrong	Correct	Wrong	Correct	Wrong	Correct	Wrong	Correct	Wrong	Correct
Prosthodontics	3	2	3	2	1	4	3	2	3	2
Endodontics	3	3	4	2	5	1	3	3	6	0
Total	6	5	7	4	6	5	6	5	9	2
p-value	0.74		0.819		0.036*		0.74		0.087	

*0<0.05; significant

Fig. 6 Comparison of shade selection in clinical light by participants from both departments

TABLE VII: THE PERCENTAGE of SELECTED SHADE TABS (from HIGHER to the LOWER) for EACH ITEM UNDER the NATURAL LIGHT SOURCE

ACTUAL SHADE	SHADE RESPONDED						
4M1	4M1	2L1.5	5M1				
	81.8	9.1	9.1				
2R1.5	2M1	2R1.5	2L1.5	1M1	2R1	3M1	
	45.5	18.2	9.1	9.1	9.1	9.1	
3M2	3M2	2M2	3M3	2M3	3L2.5	3L1.5	3R2.5
	36.4	18.2	9.1	9.1	9.1	9.1	9.1
4R2.5	4L2.5	4M2	4R2.5	5M2	4M1		
	36.4	27.3	18.2	9.1	9.1		
4L2.5	4L2.5	4R2.5	3R2.5	3M3	5M2	4M2	
	27.3	27.3	18.2	9.1	9.1	9.1	

TABLE VIII: THE PERCENTAGE of SELECTED SHADE TABS (from HIGHER to the LOWER) for EACH ITEM UNDER the CLINICAL LIGHT SOURCE

ACTUAL SHADE	SHADE RESPONDED						
4M1	4M1	2L1.5	2M2	3L1.5	3M2	3R2.5	3R1.5
	45.5	9.1	9.1	9.1	9.1	9.1	9.1
2R1.5	2R1.5	2M1	3M1	2L1.5			
	36.4	36.4	18.2	9.1			
3M2	3M2	2M2	2M3	2L2.5	2R1.5	2R2.5	
	45.5	18.2	9.1	9.1	9.1	9.1	
4R2.5	4R2.5	4L2.5	4M2	4M3	4L1.5	4R1.5	
	45.5	18.2	9.1	9.1	9.1	9.1	
4L2.5	3R2.5	4L2.5	4R2.5	3M3	4M3	4L1.5	4R1.5
	27.3	18.2	18.2	9.1	9.1	9.1	9.1

IV. DISCUSSION

In modern dentistry, great emphasis is being placed on esthetic restorations by patients and dentists.1-3 Achieving accurate and acceptable shade selection chairside, as well as precise replication in the laboratory, remains a challenging task—even for experienced clinicians and dental technicians—when working with tooth-colored restorations.

In the present study a total of 11 PG students, 5 from Department of Prosthodontics and 6 from Department of Endodontics were participated. Participants did the shade matching under various light conditions using Vita 3D master shade guide. As lighting conditions play a vital role in shade matching, two lighting conditions were used in this study, natural light and clinical light.^{[4],[5]} Study demonstrated that, under natural light,

there was less variations in shade selection. (Table 7, Table 8) It has also been reported that lighting conditions can influence the shade-matching ability of individuals with color vision deficiency, with notable improvements observed under low color temperature illumination. ^{[6]. [7]}

Vita Classic shade guide is commonly used by many practitioners. However, the major limitation of classical vita shade guide is that the numerical values do not reflect regular distribution in value and chroma. Unlike this, Vita 3D master shade guide is more systematically arranged, primarily based on value. Further shades are arranged based on their chroma and value. Hence to assess the knowledge of the participants, they are provided with a questionnaire regarding the shade selection and Vita 3D master shade guide. Though participants had basic knowledge of shade selection, questions regarding Vita 3D master shade guide were not answered correctly. None of the participants from both the departments answered correctly for questions such as “On what dimension Vita 3D master shade guide is based on?” and “What does L, M, R present on the shade guide represents?”. This showed the lack of knowledge regarding Vita 3D Master shade guide even being practiced esthetic dentistry.

As two lighting conditions have included, study also assessed the variations of shades selected by participants under both the lighting conditions. Maximum variations were seen in the clinical lighting conditions. As per the data demonstrated, Participants faced greater difficulty in matching the correct hue; when an incorrect shade tab was selected, it typically shared the same value or chroma as the correct one, but differed in hue. ^{[4]. [8]. [9]} For example, 2R1.5 was matched as 2M1 and 4R2.5 was matched as 4L2.5. This finding is also in agreement with other clinical observations which indicated that human eyes are more sensitive to value than to hue and chroma. ^[10]

The study is limited by the small sample size of just 17 participants, which affects its generalizability. Also, only shade tabs were used for shade matching while further studies are necessary to match the shades with natural teeth under different lighting conditions. Also, there is need of improvement in knowledge of participants regarding Vita 3D Master shade guide which further may alter the results of shade matching.

V. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that under the natural light better shade selection results can be achieved than clinical light. It was also observed that participants need to focus more on improving their knowledge regarding Vita 3D Master shade guide in order to achieve patient satisfaction and betterment of the treatment.

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